

IPBES VA Chapter 1 - Call for Contributions on Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK)

Code: IPBES_VA_1.1

Version: 01 (12.22.2022)

Version: 02 (03.04.2022)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4390417.

Project leader:

Ana Sofia Monroy Sais (amonroy@cieco.unam.mx)

Researcher(s)

- Brigitte Baptiste (bbaptiste@universidadean.edu.co)
- Simone Athayde (sathayde@fiu.edu)
- Elena Lazos (elena.lazos@gmail.com)
- Suneetha M. Subramanian (subramanian@unu.edu)
- Tuyeni H. Mwampamba (tuyeni@iies.unam.mx)
- Aibek Samakov (aisamakov@gmail.com)
- Liliana Bravo (libramon@uniandes.edu.co)
- Mariaelena Huambachano (mhuambac@syr.edu)
- Gabriel Nemogá (grnemogas@gmail.com)
- Sara Nelson (sara.nelson@ubc.ca)
- Ricardo Rozzi (Ricardo.Rozzi@unt.edu)
- Lelani Mannetti (lmannetti@gsu.edu)
- Luciana Porter (luciana.porter@inecol.mx)
- Juliana Merçon (julianamercon@gmail.com)
- Agnes Pawlowska-Mainville (Agnes.Pawlowska-Mainville@unbc.ca)
- Jonas Poofoun (ngouhou_p_j@yahoo.fr)

Data curator(s)

- Peter Bates (p.bates@unesco.org)
- Mariana Cantú (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Description: The IPBES Plenary, in decision IPBES-5/1, approved an approach to recognizing and working with indigenous and local knowledge in IPBES, giving IPBES an ambitious and ground-breaking process for bringing indigenous and local knowledge to the core of large-scale assessments. On June 12, 2020, a global “Call for contributions on Indigenous and Local Knowledge” was launched, in 5 different languages (Arabic, English, French, Russian, Spanish) to Invite Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLC) from all over the world to support the three ongoing IPBES assessments:

- The assessment of the sustainable use of wild species
- **The assessment on diverse conceptualisations of multiple values of nature**
- The assessment of invasive alien species

Contributions were submitted both via the IPBES website and sent to the ILK TSU electronic mail address from 12 June to 15 September 2020 by ILK holders, ILK experts and organisations. These contributions were suggestions of individuals and organisations, as well as materials (academic articles and books, artwork, videos, declarations, plans, reports, websites, journalistic articles) that contributors sent to be used for informing the IPBES assessments following FPIC principles. While the suggestions of individuals and organisations remain confidential and authors of IPBES ongoing assessments can access the names in case they are looking for a contributing author, the materials were uploaded into a Zotero shared library for authors to consult and cite. A total of 234 materials were relevant for the IPBES Values Assessment and were reviewed by the team of experts to inform their sections across all six chapters of the report.

Process overview

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Global call for contributions on Indigenous and local knowledge (August 11, 2020).

Search Languages: The call was launched in Arabic, English, French, Russian and Spanish, however, materials received were in English, French, Indonesian, Kannada, Portuguese and Spanish.

Period during which the call for contributions was open: June 12, 2020 – September 15, 2020 (Contributions were received after this date but only contributions arriving until October 2020 were reviewed for the assessment).

Sample extracted: 420 materials (until October 2020)

Fields extracted (A):

- Item type
- Publication year
- Author
- Title
- Publication title
- ISBN
- ISSN

- DOI
- URL
- Abstract
- Pages
- Num pages
- Issue
- Volume
- Language

File name (A): [IPBES_VA_1.1_October2020_\(A\).csv](#)

Treatment applied: Title, abstract and full documents (when no abstract was available) were reviewed to identify relevant documents for the values assessment and categorise them according to their relevance for the different chapters of the assessment (R1).

Sample extracted: 234 materials

Location and format of the data (B and C): [IPBES_VA_1.1_October2020_\(B\).csv](#) and [IPBES_VA_1.1_October2020_\(C\).csv](#)

Treatment applied: Documents received were used in different sections of the assessment according to the experts criteria.

Definition of files

ID	Name	Description of file	File Type	Size
A	IPBES_VA_1.1_October2020_(A).csv	Full set of contributions	csv	718 KB
B	IPBES_VA_1.1_October2020_(B).csv	Relevant documents for the assessment	csv	371 KB
C	IPBES_VA_1.1_October2020_(C).csv	Documents that were not relevant for the assessment	csv	33 KB